

FEATURES OF AUDIT AND ACTUARIAL ACTIVITIES

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Annotation: *This article discusses the main role of actuarial activities in conducting the audit of insurance companies. The research addresses issues of risks and accuracy of the accounting and reporting of business processes for auditing.*

Keywords: *financial risks, audit, actuarial calculations, insurance portfolio, actuarial audit, financial stability, solvency*

One of the areas of statistics is the development of methods for measuring financial risks. Economic entities develop measures to influence the problems that arise in their activities, based on their evaluation of the level of each risk. The significance of developing an effective risk management strategy has been increased by a number of high-profile company bankruptcies. Accepted International Financial Reporting Standards (IFRS) and International Auditing Standards (ISA) are used to develop risk assessments criteria. A risk-based approach to control has become widespread in banking and insurance, involving state control over the quality of the risk management system. Moreover, disclosure in the reporting of a quantitative assessment of the level of all significant risks, as well as ensuring such a required amount of capital, which with a high degree of probability is sufficient to cover all emerging unexpected risks, and not only insurance ones. New requirements for the quantitative assessment of insurance risks are contained in the fundamentally new IFRS 17 "Insurance Contracts" which is mandatory for use starting from January 1, 2023 in Uzbekistan. As a result, the requirement to assess risk is growing in all areas of economic activity, and the audit must take these factors into consideration. In particular, the audit looks into how insurance businesses formed and used their financial resources throughout the reporting period in accordance with established laws and regulations. It is aimed to analyze the insurer's financial stability and solvency, as well as the correctness of the formation and placement of insurance reserves, and to assess the insurer's assets, obligations, and risks.

Currently, there are some issues with insurance companies' auditing efforts. One of them is the requirement for actuarial calculations during the audit of the insurance portfolio's formation. The audit of the formation of the insurance portfolio is one of the most essential aspects of the audit of the insurer's accounting (financial) statements, as

it offers the auditor confidence in the accuracy of information concerning the activities of the insurer when forming the insurance portfolio. Basically, insurance business consists the set of business procedures like insurance portfolio, insurance reserves, insurance payments and the financial results. In accordance with the object of the audit of the insurance company, accounting and reporting materials reflecting the formation of the insurance portfolio. For instance, accounting for cash on current accounts, settlements with insurance agents, and policyholders upon receipt or return of insurance premiums are all examples of business operations. The audit's main goal is to provide an opinion on the accuracy of the accounting and reporting of business processes in the construction of the insurance portfolio. The auditor determines the insurance portfolio's degree of balance, its impact on financial stability and solvency, and the likelihood of the insurer's insolvency.

The position of actuaries-specialists in determining the financial obligations of the insurer is also taken into account while forming the insurance portfolio. However, the actuarial activity to examine the balance of the insurance portfolio serves as an addition mathematical justification to the audit activity to verify the accounting's representation of business activities. A combination of auditors' and actuaries' work is required to handle a number of financial-related challenges in insurance sphere. On the other hand, actuarial audit also has certain theoretical and practical issues. Actuarial calculations are recognized to be based on assumptions, each of which has an alternative, the actuarial audit's reliability is likewise assessed probabilistically. This information can always keep this estimate under control by adjusting the sample size, or the number of primary units of observation. Another crucial point that can be named as a limiters are time, labor and financial costs. Qualitative assessments that require scientific research are an exception to this norm. It is critical to remember that an actuarial error can be either intentional or inadvertent when conducting an actuarial audit. It can be characterized by intentional actuarial errors as systematic errors, and unintentional actuarial errors as random errors. In addition to distorting insurance companies' reporting indicators, actuarial errors violate the first criterion of insurance: the equality of the insured's and insurer's financial obligations. Insurers who make such mistakes lose, whereas insurers win.

An actuarial audit should perform a control function in relation to the insurance organization's principal activity of premium collecting, placement, and reimbursement of the insurer's costs. Generally, actuarial audit deals with insurance obligations, tariffication, insurance reserves, contractual conditions, interest rates, probability of covered events, their distribution and interaction, and various discounts and capes. The financial flows of an insurance organization, the structure of its asset and liability balance sheet, and the planning and budgeting of insurance activities - all fall within the scope of actuarial audit, as it is a derivative of the initial contract between the insured and the insurer on the one hand, and the final expression and result of this

activity on the other. The auditor's attention is called to probable limits and deviations from genuine values or standards of the basic characteristics used in actuarial calculations. There may also be inaccuracies in actuarial calculation methods, statistical indicator replacement (substitution), and other factors may also exist.

Overall, the task of the auditor is to ensure the validity of the actuarial calculations carried out within the insurance company, accordingly, the correctness of the statistical and accounting reports reflected in the financial statements of insurance companies. It can be said that an actuarial audit is integral part of the general audit of an insurance company, without which the audit itself is meaningless.

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